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RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN BANK SERVICE QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of retail service quality on customer satisfaction. This study identified six important dimensions of bank service quality. They are core service, service delivery, trust, reliability, competence and tangibles. The researchers used structured questionnaire method for collecting data from the respondents and systematic random sampling method has been used. This study proved that except reliability dimensions, all the dimensions of bank service quality has influence on customer satisfaction. This study finding would help the management to frame suitable policies relating to bank service quality.

Keywords: Trust, competence, tangibles, core service, service delivery.

INTRODUCTION:

Banks are considered to be the backbone of every economy and it is important to mention the role of banking in the trending economies because of the fast advances in information technology and entry of private sector banks and financial market forms. The survival of banks depends on the service quality and in the banking sector research has found the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty (Ndubisi and Wah, 2005; Lenka et al., 2009; Bedi, 2010; Ganguli and Roy, 2011; Kaura and Datta, 2012). The service evaluation has dimensions such as price, systemization, servicescape and social responsibility (Dutta and Dutta, 2009). So, there is a need to consider the service quality of banks in estimating their retention and growth. Improved service quality increased the customer satisfaction in Indian Banking Sector (Lenka et al, 2009; Bedi, 2010; kaura and Datta, 2012). Customer retention is more important than customer attraction as attracting the customers is more costlier than retaining the customers. During the past two decades regulatory, structural and technological factors have tremendously changed the banking environment throughout the world (Angur et al., 1999). In the Indian banking sector, people factor has a

positive impact on customer satisfaction (Kaura and Datta, 2012). Service quality and satisfaction has the relationship in which service quality perception affects the satisfaction which influences the purchasing behaviour (Hurley and Estelami, 1998). The purpose of the research is to examine the service quality of banks towards the customers as they were the ultimate beneficiaries. The primary value of SERVQUAL lies in its powerful benchmarking, diagnostic, and prescriptive tools (Kettinger and Lee, 1997). Service quality has five dimensions such as tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy (Parasuraman et al, 1988).Service quality has been shown to be valid for a number of service situations and has a standardised analysis procedure to aid interpretation and results. To protect or gain market shares, organizations need to outperform competitors in offering satisfaction to customers (Reich held and sasser, 1990). Service quality is considered as difficult to explain and measure (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). Customer service has a vital role in an organization's success and failure in the current business scenario (Mouawad&Kleiner, 1996).Service quality is a measure of how well the service level delivered matches customer expectations. Service quality has become an area of attraction to practitioners, managers owing to its strong impact on business performance, lower costs, customer satisfaction and loyalty (Leonard and Sasser, 1982). Banks need to understand customers service requirements and know the impact of service delivery performance in customer attitudes(Gerrard and Cunningham,2001). Service quality not only influences the satisfaction of buyers but also their purchase intentions. Service quality offers customer satisfaction and purchase intentions (Rust and Zahorik, 1993). Banks offering the specialised quality service has the impact of addition of customers. Measuring the quality act as a challenge as quality can be interpreted in different ways (Finn and Lamb, 1991). It is well known that the models of service quality will enable the management in identifying the quality problems and for implementing the quality program which inturn improves the efficiency, profitability and overall performance(Ghobadian et al,1994).The interest is largely driven by the realization that high service quality results in customer satisfaction and loyalty, greater willingness to recommend to someone else, reduction in complaints and improved customer retention rates(Bitner,1990). Service quality has impact on satisfaction which in turn affects the financial performance of banks (Al-Hawari and Ward, 2006). The increasing importance of services and growing competitions, the consumers and management must pay special attention to the service quality. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Review of literature, research objectives, research methodology, managerial implication and future directions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

The functional quality refers to “how” the service is delivered, while the outcome or technical quality refers to “what” customers receive, the benefits of using the service (Gronroos, 1984). The studies suggested that research is needed on “the definitions and relative importance of the service quality dimensions change when customers interact with technology rather than with service personnel” (Parasuraman and Grewal, 2000). Bolton and Drew (1991) studied the role of customers prior expectations and experiences in assessing the overall service quality and performance. Regarding banks, customer longevity can only be achieved through delivering high quality services (Berry et al., 1985; Capon et al., 1990). Service quality apart from being generic might lack the potential to grasp the particularities of the industry and it is widely used in banking services assessment (Angur et al., 1999; Newman, 2001; Dash, 2006). Customers judgement “related but not equivalent to satisfaction” of the overall excellence or superiority of a service (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

Service quality via customer satisfaction determined customer loyalty suggesting that customers satisfaction promoted their loyalty in Indian Banking Sector (Lenka et al., 2009). Thus customer satisfaction plays as mediating variable between service quality and customer loyalty. The technology based service quality in banking has an impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty (Ganguli, s and Roy, s.k, 2011). A study conducted by Kaura and Datta (2012) found that people factor has a positive impact on customer satisfaction in the Indian Banking sector. The tangible aspects of service quality of the bank branches enhance customer satisfaction (Lenka et al, 2009). Most of the items of service quality focus on human aspects of service delivery with the remaining on tangibles (Sureshchandar et al, 2002). Satisfaction act as mediating variable between service quality and purchase intentions (Cronin et al, 2000). Delivering quality service means conforming to customer expectations on a consistent basis (Lewis and Booms, 1983). Bedi, M. (2010) made an integrated framework for service quality, customer satisfaction and behavioural responses in Indian Banking industry in comparison of public and private sector banks. Although several studies have been conducted, most of the studies have been conducted in foreign countries. Therefore, the researcher would like to fill the gap by studying the factors influencing service quality and customer satisfaction.

3. PROPOSED RESEARCH MODEL:

This study is approached with the following proposed research model.

3.1. Proposed Hypothesis:

H_{01} : Core service will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction

H_{02} : Service delivery will have no significant impact on customer Satisfaction.

H_{03} : Trust will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction.

H_{04} : Reliability will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction.

H_{05} : Competence will have no significant impact on customer Satisfaction.

H_{06} : Tangibles will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction.

3.2 Research Objectives:

The specific objectives of the study are

- 1) To determine the factors that leads to customer satisfaction as regards to bank service quality.
- 2) To examine the impact of bank service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction.

4. METHODOLOGY:

The target population of this study is Bank customers in Erode district. Before conducting survey, the researchers approached 20 banks to participate the study. Out of 20 banks, only eight banks accepted the invitation and allowed the customers to participate in the study. This study has been conducted over a period of eight months from bank customers from December 2015 to July 2016. The researchers used structured questionnaire method for collecting data from the respondents. This technique has proven to be successfully used in a variety of service marketing researches (Bitner et al, 1990, Gwinner et al, 1998). The researchers used systematic random sampling methods for collecting data from the bank customers. The questionnaire consists of three important components, the first part of the questionnaire consist of demographic profile of the respondents, the second part consist of variables relating to bank service quality and third part of the questionnaire consist of variables relating to customer satisfaction. A total of 538 questionnaires were distributed among the bank customers and and 239 questionnaires (44 percent) were returned. Before administering the questionnaire to the respondents, the questionnaire was pre-tested on 22 respondents and based on their feedback necessary modifications were made in the existing questionnaire to suit the requirement of the present study.

4.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents:

Out of the collected data, 58 percent of the respondents are male category. 43 percent of the respondents had degree level education as their qualification. Above 32 percent of the customers were between the age of 35 to 45 years. 82 percent of the respondents are married and 38 percent of the respondents occupation is Business, 43 percent of the respondents have more than one bank account, 63 percent of the respondents have relationship with the bank for more than 3 years.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Prior to applying factor analysis, the reliability of the bank service quality score was checked with the help of Cronbach alpha to assess the internal consistency of the entire data (Malhotra, 2008). The reliability estimates for the bank service quality dimension are as follows: core service (0.709), service delivery (0.792), trust (0.813), reliability (0.769), competence (0.713) and tangibles (0.784). The results exceed 0.60, the lower limit of acceptability recommended by Hair et al (1998).

Table 1: Reliability of the Data

Sl. No	Service quality dimensions	No of original statements	No of statements retained	Cronbach alpha
1	Core service	6	5	0.709
2	Service delivery	6	5	0.792
3	Trust	6	6	0.813
4	Reliability	5	5	0.769
5	Competence	5	5	0.713
6	Tangibles	5	5	0.784

Factor analysis was performed on all bank service quality questionnaire items to establish their suitability for performing further multivariate analysis. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olin measure of sampling adequacy gives a high total of 0.638 and Bartlett's test of sphericity value is significant ($p=0.000$). The first underlying dimension of the factor analysis is core service, which consists of five variables with Eigen value of 3.538. The second dimension consists of variables that relate to service delivery and five items were loaded on this factor. The third dimension is the trust. It consists of five items that relate to trust. The fourth dimension consists of elements that relates to reliability which consists of five variables. The fifth dimension consists of items that relate to competence which consist of five variables each. The last dimension consists of variables that relates to tangibles.

Table 2: Service Quality Dimensions In Banking Sector

Sl. No	Service quality dimensions	No of variables included	Eigen value	Percentage of variance explained	Cumulative percentage of variance explained
1	Core service	5	3.538	26.505	26.505
2	Service delivery	5	1.758	8.234	34.739
3	Trust	6	1.539	6.993	41.732
4	Reliability	5	1.459	6.745	48.477
5	Competence	5	1.263	6.343	54.820
6	Tangibles	5	1.173	6.216	61.037

KMO measures of sampling adequacy 0.638	Bartlett's test of sphericity 0.210
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5.3 Influence of Bank Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction:

In order to study the influence of bank service quality on customer satisfaction, regression analysis was used. The fitted regression model is

$$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + e$$

Y=customer satisfaction

a=intercept

e=error term

X_1 =mean score on core service

X_2 = mean score on service delivery.

X_3 =mean score on trust

X_4 =mean score on reliability

X_5 =mean score on competence

X_6 =mean score on tangibles

$\beta_{1,2,3,4,5,6}$ -Regression co efficient of bank service quality dimensions.

The results show that the adjusted R^2 explain 59.2 percent of the variance in bank service quality on customer satisfaction. The ANOVA table revealed that the regression model is statistically significant and bank service quality variables have a systematic association with the customer satisfaction. As can be seen in table3 service delivery has positive impact on bank customer satisfaction ($\beta=0.305, t=4.205, p<0.01$) and tangibles($\beta=0.229, t=3.267, p<0.01$). Findings related to trust reveals that it has a positive impact on customer satisfaction ($\beta =0.209, t=3.153, p<0.01$) and core service quality($\beta=0.202, t=2.850, p<0.05$). Competence shows positive impact on bank customer satisfaction ($\beta =0.168, t=2.443, p<0.05$)

Table 3: Influence of Bank Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

Sl. No	Independent variables	Standardised coefficients	t	sigma	Co linearity statistics		
					Tolerance	VIF	
1	Constant	-	2.427	0.017	-	-	
2	Core service	0.202	2.850	0.005	0.815	1.226	
3	Service delivery	0.305	4.205	0.000	0.780	1.282	
4	Trust	0.209	3.153	0.002	0.931	1.074	
5	Reliability	0.124	1.805	0.074	0.866	1.155	
6	Competence	0.168	2.443	0.016	0.863	1.159	
7	Tangibles	0.229	3.267	0.001	0.830	1.205	
r square						0.554	
Adjusted r square						0.529	
F statistics						22.562	
Significance		0.000					

Table 4: Testing of Hypothesis

HYPOTHESIS	BETA	RESULTS
H_{01} :core service will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction	0.202	Rejected
H_{02} :service quality will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction	0.305	Rejected
H_{03} : Trust will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction	0.209	Rejected
H_{04} : Reliability will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction	0.124	accepted
H_{05} : Competence will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction	0.168	Rejected
H_{06} : Tangibles will have no significant impact on customer satisfaction	0.229	Rejected

6. CONCLUSION:

This study identified six important dimensions of service quality. They are: core service, service delivery, trust, reliability, competence and tangibles. The results of this study revealed that core service, service delivery, trust, competence and tangibles are important determinants of customer satisfaction as regards bank service quality. Since service quality of the bank is considered by the customers before selecting the bank, bank managers can make use of service quality related information for formulating policies. This study considers only limited variables. In future, several variables can also be incorporated.

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